

Multicomponent analysis of a ternary mixture of paracetamol, ibuprofen and caffeine in Novafen capsules with the aid of chemometrics

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Abstract : Net analyte signal standard addition method (NASSAM) has been presented for the simultaneous determination of paracetamol, ibuprofen and caffeine by spectrophotometry. The method combines the advantages of the standard addition method with the net analyte signal concept which enables the extraction of information concerning a certain analyte from spectra of multi-component mixtures. This method has some advantages such as the use of a full spectrum realization in determination step, therefore, it does not require calibration and prediction steps and only a few measurements are required for the determination. The simultaneous determination of paracetamol, ibuprofen and caffeine was performed in Britton-Robinson buffer (pH 10.0). Three pharmaceutical compounds were determined in concentration ranges of 0.4–320 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, 0.4–240 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ and 0.4–260 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ respectively. For study the accuracy of the proposed method, NASSAM has been successfully applied to the simultaneous determination of pharmaceutical compounds in some synthetic and pharmaceutical formulations (Novafen capsules) with the recoveries in the range of 84.3–108.7% with the RSD (%) of 0.43–3.9%.

Keywords : Paracetamol, ibuprofen, caffeine, NASSAM, Novafen.

Introduction

Paracetamol (Fig. 1A), ibuprofen (Fig. 1B) and caffeine (Fig. 1C) are active principles widely used and frequently combined in pharmaceutical preparations. PAR is a popular antipyretic and analgesic agent¹. In several countries, it is one of the most used medicines as an alternative to aspirin (acetylsalicylic acid). IBU is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug with good analgesic, anti-inflammatory and antipyretic effects². CAF, a methylated xanthine and potent stimulant of the central nervous system, has been added to PRT and IB in various combinations. This addition seems to be aimed at improving the analgesic efficacy^{3,4}.

Various methods, including official methods^{5–7}, spectrophotometry^{8–13}, spectrofluorometry¹⁴ and chromatography^{15–20} are available for the determination of above compounds, whether alone or in combination with other drugs. The quality control of dosage form preparations of drug requires reliable and quick analytical methods. UV/Vis spectrophotometry is by far the instrumental tech-

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of paracetamol (A), ibuprofen (B) and caffeine (C).

nique of choice in industrial laboratories, owing mainly to its simplicity and often demanding low cost equipment. Simultaneous quantitative analysis of pharmaceuticals containing multi-active compounds is difficult to perform by classical spectrophotometric method due to overlapping spectra.

Multivariate calibration methods such as principal component regression (PCR) and partial least squares (PLS) are useful chemometric techniques for the calculation of concentration of one species in a multicomponent samples by overlapping spectra²¹. PCR and PLS methods use inverse calibration steps and have some advantages such as (i) use of full spectra, (ii) knowledge of only the concentrations of the analytes of interest in the calibration samples is required and (iii) spectral decomposition into factors avoids the problems associated with spectral collinearities²¹. The most difficult in the application of these multivariate calibration methods is human decisions in the selection of the number of factors²². With the introduction and development of the useful concept of net analyte signal (NAS)²³, a new family of multivariate calibration methods has been arisen²⁴⁻²⁶. The NAS is the part of the signal which is directly related to the concentration predicted by the calibration model. In mathematical terms, it is the part of a spectrum which is orthogonal to the space spanned by the spectra of all analytes except one²³. There were four net analyte signal based methods reported in the literature : (i) Hybrid linear analysis (HLA)²⁴, which can be applied a very accurately measured pure spectrum of the analyte is available. (ii) The HLA method developed by Xu and Schechter (HLA/XS)²² that uses all the factors for prediction, in order to build a method free from optimum factor estimation. (iii) The HLA also, developed by Goicoechea and Olivieri (HLA/GO) which extract interferences subspace with removing the analyte portion²⁵. (iv) Other NAS-based multivariate calibration methods have also been proposed in which the vectors of NAS of mixtures are used as input for other multivariate calibration methods such as classical least squares (NAS/CLS), principal component regression (NAS/PCR) and partial least squares regression (NAS/PLS)²⁶⁻³⁰.

Recently Asadpor-Zeynali *et al.* introduced a novel method for determination of an analyte in the presence of known interferences called "net analyte signal standard

addition method (NASSAM)"³¹. The proposed method uses the NAS to construct a univariate calibration model and combines with those of standard addition equations.

In this work, a sensitive, selective, accurate and inexpensive procedure was applied for simultaneous determination of ibuprofen, caffeine and paracetamol by net analyte signal standard addition method. In this research, an attempt was made to calculate the norm of net analyte signal and attribute it to the analyte concentration using UV-Visible spectrophotometry technique. The method can be applied for the determination of analyte in the presence of known interferences and the accuracy of the predictions does not depend on the shape of the analyte and interferent spectra.

Theoretical aspect :

The net analyte signal (NAS) was defined by Lorber²³ based on spectroscopic methods, as the part of a spectrum for a mixture that is independent to all of the interferences spectra, i.e. it is orthogonal to the space of interferences.

For more understanding about the concept of NAS, consider a synthetic mixture containing X, Y and Z in concentrations of 10 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for each analyte. The simultaneous determination of three analytes by NASSAM requires having the spectrum vector of the mixture. The standard concentrations of X, Y and Z are simultaneously added to the sample solution. The spectrum of the mixture after each standard addition is recorded base on the following equations :

$$A_0 = \epsilon_X C_X^0 + \epsilon_Y C_Y^0 + \epsilon_Z C_Z^0 \quad (1)$$

$$A_1 = A_0 + \epsilon_X C_{X,s_1} + \epsilon_Y C_{Y,s_1} + \epsilon_Z C_{Z,s_1} \quad (2)$$

$$A_i = A_{i-1} + \epsilon_X C_{X,s_i} + \epsilon_Y C_{Y,s_i} + \epsilon_Z C_{Z,s_i} \quad (3)$$

$$A_n = A_{n-1} + \epsilon_X C_{X,s_n} + \epsilon_Y C_{Y,s_n} + \epsilon_Z C_{Z,s_n} \quad (4)$$

where A_0 and A_i are the absorbances of the synthetic mixtures before and after of standard additions. C_X^0 , C_Y^0 , C_Z^0 and C_{X,s_i} , C_{Y,s_i} , C_{Z,s_i} are the initial added concentrations of X, Y and Z to the sample in the i -th step. Also ϵ_X , ϵ_Y and ϵ_Z are molar absorptivities of X, Y and Z respectively.

The NAS vectors for X, Y and Z compounds after each standard addition, $\text{NAS}_{X,i}$, $\text{NAS}_{Y,i}$ and $\text{NAS}_{Z,i}$ can be found by the following equations respectively :

$$\text{NAS}_{X_i} = (I - R^+R)A_i \quad (5)$$

$$\text{NAS}_{Y_i} = (I - S^+S)A_i \quad (6)$$

$$\text{NAS}_{Z_i} = (I - T^+T)A_i \quad (7)$$

where I is an identical matrix, R , S and T are the matrixes of absorbances in different concentrations of both interferences. Based on the eqs. (5) to (7), the spectrum of the mixture (A_i) is the combination of two independent parts i.e. NAS_X , which is orthogonal to the space of interferences (Y and Z) and also $(R^+R)A_i$. Where $(R^+R)A_i$ is a part of the spectrum that is generated by a linear combination of the spectra of the interfering agents. The superscript $+$ indicates the pseudo inverse of a non-square matrix. Consequently, $(R^+R)A_i$ is not independent to the concentration of interferences. The other part NAS_X is orthogonal to the space of interferences (X and Y). Therefore it is dependent only to the concentration of X in the mixture. Therefore the orthogonal vectors of X , Y and Z which known as NAS_X , NAS_Y and NAS_Z correlate with the concentrations of analytes (X , Y and Z) respectively. Fig. 2 shows the geometrical presentation of NAS vectors. As it has shown, the norm of the NAS_X vector depends only to the concentration of X in the mixture. Therefore it can be used as a net signal to correlate with analyte concentrations.

Fig. 2. Representation of vector space for analyte (X) and other analytes (Y and Z) in two dimensional space. NAS vector NAS_X is different from X vector in direction and length.

In this work, the norm of the NAS for each analyte in the ternary mixture is calculated and correlates to each analyte concentration. This correlation is linear and in

the case of matrix effect, standard addition plots can be constructed against added standard additions.

Experimental

Chemicals :

Paracetamol, ibuprofen hydrochloride and caffeine were kindly provided by Iranian Pharmaceutical Companies (Tehran, Iran). Analytical grade phosphoric acid, boric acid, acetic acid and sodium hydroxide supplied from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). All other reagents were of analytical grade.

Britton-Robinson (B-R) buffer (0.1 mol L^{-1}) in the pH range of 2–10 was used throughout.

A $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ paracetamol solution was prepared daily by dissolving 0.0148 g PAR (99.0%) in ethanol (96%) and was diluted in a 100 ml volumetric flask to the mark. A $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ ibuprofen hydrochloride solution was prepared daily by dissolving 0.0206 g of IBU (99.5%) in ethanol (96%) and diluted in a 100 ml volumetric flask. A $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ caffeine solution was prepared daily by dissolving 0.0194 g of CAF (99.5%) in double distilled water and diluted into a 100 ml volumetric flask. These solutions kept in a refrigerator at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in dark. More dilute solutions were prepared by several dilutions with double distilled water.

Instrumentation and software :

UV-Visible absorption spectra were recorded by a spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer) model Lambda 25, with the use of 1.0 cm quartz cells.

A Pentium IV (2.53 GHz) computer controlled all the setting and data processing. All spectra transformed to an in house Matlab program (R2008a) to calculate the norm of NAS vectors.

A pH-meter (Metrohm, Model 827) with a double junction glass electrode was used to adjust pH of the solutions.

Preparation of real samples :

To assay Novafen capsule containing paracetamol (325 mg), ibuprofen (200 mg) and caffeine (40 mg) in each capsule, the content of five capsules mixed together. The quantity of 0.0263 g of the powder was accurately weighted and then dissolved in 100 mL of ethanol (96%). After mixing completely, the solution was diluted to the mark with ethanol. This solution was kept in refrigerator at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and finally diluted 10 times in the determination step.

General procedure :

The general procedure used to obtain NAS-SAM was as follows. To approximately 1.0 ml of sample solution in a 5.0 ml volumetric flask, 1.0 ml B-R buffer (pH 10.0) added and the final volume diluted to the mark with distilled water after successive standard additions of three species (PAR, IBU and CAF) at the same mole ratios. The spectrum of each mixture was recorded in the wavelength range of 210–320 nm and saved as text files. For calculation the norm of NAS vector for each analyte, the matrixes of R, S and T designed according to the concentration ranges of Table 1. Then the text files transferred to Matlab program for calculation of norms (eqs. (5)–(7)). In the end, the concentration of each component was calculated by standard addition plot (Norm of NAS vs added concentrations).

Table 1. The concentrations of ACE, IBU and CAF used in the interferent matrixes of R, S and T for calculation of NAS

Matrix R		Matrix S		Matrix T	
IBU	CAF	ACE	CAF	ACE	IBU
1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2
4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0
20.0	20.0	20.0	20.0	20.0	20.0
40.0	40.0	40.0	40.0	40.0	40.0
60.0	60.0	60.0	60.0	60.0	60.0
80.0	80.0	80.0	80.0	80.0	80.0
100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
120.0	120.0	120.0	120.0	120.0	120.0

Results and discussion*Initial investigation :*

To demonstrate the analytical applicability of the proposed method for the analysis of ternary mixtures, three pure spectra of PAR, IBU and CAF were recorded separately. As it is shown in Fig. 3, the spectra are too overlapped in the range of 210–320 nm. Fig. 4 shows successive standard addition of three analytes (PAR, IBU and CAF) in a certain ratio into an unknown mixture. Fig. 4 shows that simultaneous determination of three compounds is possible by one standard addition step. Therefore the total number of recording spectra and preparing solutions decrease in this procedure. NAS vectors for components were calculated simultaneously based on eqs. (5)–(7) (Fig. 5) and the norm of each NAS vector plotted against standard added concentrations that could be used to cal-

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of paracetamol (A), ibuprofen (B) and caffeine (C) at B-R buffer pH 10.0. The concentration of each component is $10 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$.

Fig. 4. The spectra after addition of standard solutions containing PAR, IBU and CAF at the same mole ratios in the concentration range of $10\text{--}60 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for spectra 2–7. The initial solution contains a mixture of PAR ($10 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$), IBU ($10 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) and CAF ($10 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$).

culate the simultaneous concentrations of each analyte respectively. A typical standard addition plot has been shown in Fig. 6.

Effect of pH :

Influence of the variables potentially affecting the absorption spectra was studied. The only studied parameter was pH. pH of the solution is an important parameter that may be affects on the sensitivity and selectivity of the procedure. As it has shown in Fig. 7A and B, the maximum absorbances for PAR, IBU and CAF are independence to pH in terms of sensitivity and overlapping. Consequently, alkali media (pH 10.0) was selected for elimination of probably cationic ions. Table 2 shows analytical characteristics for PAR, IBU and CAF determination under optimum experimental conditions by spectrophotometric method.

Fig. 5. NAS vectors for (A) acetaminophen, (B) ibuprofen and (C) caffeine calculated from the spectra recorded in Fig. 4.

Fig. 6. Typical standard addition plot derived by the norms of NAS vectors calculated in Fig. 5.

Fig. 7. The effect of pH on the A_{\max} (A) and λ_{\max} (B) for PAR, IBU and CAF using B-R buffer. Conditions : ACE, 10.0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$; IBU, 40.0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ and CAF, 10.0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$.

Table 2. Calibration data for the determination of paracetamol, ibuprofen and caffeine by NASSAM

Component	λ_{\max} (nm)	Linearity range ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)	Equation	R^2
ACE	248	0.4–320	$Y = 0.0086X - 0.0080$	0.9999
IBU	221	0.4–240	$Y = 0.0091X + 0.0519$	0.9998
CAF	273	0.4–260	$Y = 0.0094X - 0.0020$	0.9992

NASSAM for spectrophotometric determination :

The proposed method was evaluated in the assay of some synthetic mixtures (Table 3) and commercial tablets (Novafen, Table 4). Three replicate determinations were carried out on each experiment. These results confirm satisfactory to the label claim and indicate the high precision and accuracy of the proposed method when applied to tablets (see Table 4).

The results of the reproducibility for the proposed method have shown in Table 5. The average of the calculated RSD (%) were 1.38, 2.66 and 1.61% ($n = 3$) for PAR, IBU and CAF respectively.

Table 3. Simultaneous determination of acetaminophen, ibuprofen and caffeine in some synthetic mixtures by the proposed method

Mixture	Added ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			Found ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			Recovery (%)		
	ACE	IBU	CAF	ACE	IBU	CAF	ACE	BU	CAF
1	40.0	20.0	30.0	39.6	21.4	31.8	99.0	105.0	106.0
2	10.0	20.0	10.0	10.2	21.0	10.7	101.6	105.0	107.0
3	8.0	10.0	20.0	8.0	11.0	21.9	102.5	110.0	109.5
4	8.0	30.0	10.0	8.3	31.5	10.6	103.7	105.0	106.0
5	30.0	40.0	20.0	32.9	41.2	22.0	109.6	103.0	109.9
6	50.0	50.0	50.0	48.4	53.4	49.8	96.8	106.0	99.6
7	30.0	60.0	30.0	32.5	59.7	30.0	108.3	99.5	100.0
8	20.0	70.0	30.0	20.4	69.9	29.8	101.9	99.9	99.3
9	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.9	10.9	10.1	108.8	109.0	101.0
10	40.0	10.0	40.0	40.9	40.9	42.2	105.3	104.9	105.5

Table 4. Determination of acetaminophen, ibuprofen and caffeine in some pharmaceutical formulations by NASSAM, expressed as

$$\bar{X} \pm (tS.D.) / \sqrt{N}, \text{ for } N=3 \text{ measurements and } t_{95\%, (N-1=2)} = 2.92$$

Sample ^a	Added ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			Found ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			Recovery (%)		
	ACE	IBU	CAF	ACE	IBU	CAF	ACE	BU	CAF
Brand 1	-	-	-	328.13 \pm 4.44	207.16 \pm 8.54	40.72 \pm 3.30	101.0	103.6	101.8
	44.34	32.50	41.71	363.45 \pm 2.10	244.55 \pm 4.60	81.29 \pm 3.35	108.7	84.3	97.3
Brand 2	-	-	-	328.69 \pm 1.10	187.76 \pm 1.36	38.95 \pm 1.07	101.1	93.9	97.4
	44.34	32.50	41.71	360.29 \pm 3.70	232.65 \pm 2.56	79.92 \pm 1.55	97.2	101.2	98.2
Brand 3	-	-	-	326.53 \pm 0.53	196.38 \pm 5.82	39.72 \pm 1.23	100.5	98.2	99.3
	44.34	65.00	41.71	392.58 \pm 0.60	246.62 \pm 0.60	82.87 \pm 3.38	101.6	113.3	103.5
Brand 4	-	-	-	331.65 \pm 0.29	196.82 \pm 5.04	39.57 \pm 3.58	102.0	98.4	98.9
	44.34	32.50	41.71	365.62 \pm 0.84	239.16 \pm 8.43	78.79 \pm 0.08	104.5	96.9	94.0
Brand 5	-	-	-	320.88 \pm 3.77	186.28 \pm 4.69	37.66 \pm 1.84	74.0	93.1	94.2
	44.34	65.00	41.71	379.42 \pm 0.89	230.59 \pm 0.95	123.89 \pm 4.35	90.0	99.9	103.1

^aBrands 1 to 5 are pharmaceutical capsules manufactured by Alhavi, Farmachimi, Kish Medipharm and Saha Pharmaceutical Companies respectively. Each brand contains acetaminophen (325 mg), ibuprofen (200 mg) and caffeine (40 mg) in each capsule.

Table 5. Relative standard deviation for ACE, IBU and CAF calculated by NASSAM for some synthetic mixtures

Mixture	Added ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			Found ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			RSD (%)		
	ACE	IBU	CAF	ACE	IBU	CAF	ACE	BU	CAF
1	10.0	10.0	10.0	9.0	10.1	10.5			
	10.0	10.0	10.0	9.6	10.1	10.0	3.7	1.3	2.5
	10.0	10.0	10.0	9.6	10.3	10.3			
2	40.0	40.0	40.0	37.1	38.8	39.0			
	40.0	40.0	40.0	37.5	38.2	40.4	0.43	1.57	2.0
	40.0	40.0	40.0	37.3	37.6	40.3			
3	10.0	30.0	50.0	9.6	28.9	51.0			
	10.0	30.0	50.0	9.7	28.7	50.7	3.9	1.3	
	10.0	30.0	50.0	10.3	28.2	50.7			

Conclusions

Quantification of paracetamol, ibuprofen and caffeine has been accomplished from spectrophotometric data with

a novel method based on NAS and standard addition method. In the present of known interferences, the part of the mixture spectrum that is orthogonal to the

interferent's space can be calculated as NAS and this is attributed to analyte concentration. In two popular multivariate calibration methods i.e. PCR and PLS, we should select optimum number of factors or principal components. This selection may lead to overfitting and/or underfitting. This restriction is deleted in the proposed method without factor selection. The proposed method is useful for the determination of analytes in mixtures by spectrophotometric without a prior separation or special conditions to resolve the analytes spectra. The ensuring method is simple, inexpensive, precise and affordable; also they require no complex pretreatment. So, it is suggested to be used in routine analysis of mixtures of analytes giving overlapped spectra.

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